

Oral History Projects' Multiple Frames of Reference: Implications for Stewardship

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ABSTRACT

This paper for SIG-USE reports work in progress on exploring documentary practices for oral history projects through the lens of human information behavior. It is the first study to thematize sensitizing concepts in LIS as tools to analyze information uses in the oral history format. Sensitizing concepts on information practice, information work, and communities of practice foreground human-centeredness in information work contexts. On-site research using qualitative content analysis techniques took place in fall 2022 to determine two units of analysis and investigate census and purposive samples of oral histories at the Science History Institute, Philadelphia, PA. Results suggest that documentary practices reflect information use by stakeholders whose multiple frames of reference layer visible and invisible work in the conception, production, and documentation of oral history projects and co-authored interviews. The conclusion offers three directions for future research. Recommendations include conceptualizing stewardship as collaborative information practices and attributing information work.

KEYWORDS

Information behavior, information practice, metadata, stewardship, oral history, invisible work.

INTRODUCTION

Human-centeredness in the oral history genre holds untapped interest for information scientists studying human information behavior. Enfolding multiple agents in the production of oral history projects, the genre exemplifies intriguing uses of information through collaborative social processes. However, an epistemological framework for the social construction of knowledge in oral history projects is lacking. This paper reports work in progress exploring information contexts and uses of oral history projects through qualitative content analysis techniques applied to census and purposive samples of oral histories in the Science History Institute in Philadelphia, PA. First, a literature review describes the oral history genre and frames a gap in human information behavior research. Next, a methods section outlines content analysis methods appropriate for the work in progress. Third, findings outline data collection and analysis, and fourth, results interpret findings. Fifth, discussion develops the substance of work in progress and its limitations. A conclusion revisits key points and makes recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Background on the oral history genre

Oral histories are primary documents, each a “historical source” (Treleven, 2000, p. 126). A key tenet of the oral history genre is its credibility as documentation of “historiographical” issues through purposeful selection of interviewees (“narrators”) matched to oral history practitioners (“interviewers”) (Grele & Terkel, 1991, p. 131). Narrators and interviewers engage in “joint activities, organized and informed by the historical perspectives of both participants” (Grele & Terkel, 1991, p. 136). Authority of the work is shared “by definition—in the dialogic nature of the interview, in the history-making offered by both interviewer and narrator” (Frisch, 2003, p. 113). Over the course of hours and even days, dialog probes the narrator’s social networks and major career and life decisions. Two approaches to the collection of oral history data in the literatures of archival science and oral history include, one, filling gaps in existing archives (of individuals or subject areas), and two, fulfilling oral history projects. Because the resources and expertise required for a single oral history can be daunting, scaling the concept gained momentum in the 1960s. Fittingly enough, James V. Mink relates in an interview with Dale Treleven that he organized the first national oral history colloquium in 1966 as archivist of UCLA and director of its inaugural oral history program (Treleven, 2000). Oral history programs at academic institutions were subsequently established at University of California at Los Angeles, Columbia University, University of Texas at Waco, and the University of Illinois. The oral history program at Science History Institute dates the earliest oral history in the collection 1979 and the most recent 2021.

Oral histories and human information behavior research in library and information science

Oral histories merit study by information scientists whose research methods adhere to the human-centered interpretivist tradition of qualitative research, in which reality is construed as the co-existence of multiple viewpoints bearing on the social construction of knowledge in natural settings (Charmaz, 2014; Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Pickard, 2017). The areas of information practice (IP) and information work (IW) branched out from cognitive models for human information behavior research (HIB) in library and information science (LIS) (Fulton & Henefer, 2018; Huvila, 2008; Savolainen, 2007; Wilson, 2009). Exploration of social groups’ information use in natural settings, including work contexts broadly defined as spaces for purposeful human activities, is congruent with the social construction of knowledge. IP concepts encompass embodiment and affect in meaningful social exchange,

while IW insights prioritize workers’ perspectives and trajectories of information work (Corbin & Strauss, 1988; Hogan & Palmer, 2006; Lloyd, 2007; Strauss et al., 1985; Veinot, 2007). Complementing IP and IW, COP concepts highlight informal group cohesion, resistance to authority, and dispersion with or without trace (Davies, 2009; Lave & Wenger, 1991). Notions of visible and invisible work dynamics in COP as well as IP and IW concepts, not least, afford insights into fluid frames of reference for negotiating work definition while allocating labor and accountability (Dalmer & Huvila, 2019; McKenzie, 2003; Star, 1991; Strauss, 1988; Wenger, 1998). In sum, interrelated themes across IP, IW, and COP literature are usefully grouped as sensitizing concepts, a theoretical tool for focusing the analysis and interpretation of information use in information-intensive settings such as memory institutions. Given multiple agents in the conception and production of oral history projects, the research question explores the social production of documentation: How can sensitizing concepts in LIS areas of IP, IW, and COP research elucidate information use in oral history projects?

METHODS

Content analysis in quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods research

The work in progress utilizes qualitative content analysis techniques to explore the research question. The techniques span quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods, yet the centrality of human interpretation of textual content aligns well with qualitative research (Bernard & Ryan, 2010; Krippendorff, 2013b; Zhang & Wildemuth, 2009). Determining one or more contexts for the texts under scrutiny through data preparation and inductive reasoning aids coding, so that meanings emerge from the analytical process while grounded in data (Krippendorff, 2013a; Zhang & Wildemuth, 2009). The sample’s base at Science History Institute constitutes a geographic boundary in the city of Philadelphia. Units of analysis include project sponsoring entities and oral history transcripts. Criteria for a purposive sample narrow focus to a major funder of an underserved group as determined by filters provided by Science History Institute: women scientists whose oral history interviews were sponsored by Pew Charitable Trusts. Data collection began in September 2022 and was coded in NVivo and Excel spreadsheets. With preparation to ensure trustworthiness, data analysis supports thick description of social contexts and phenomena that produce textual data. Malleability of researcher intent is a strength in content analysis; likewise, the availability and static nature of textual data permit unobtrusive data collection (Wildemuth, 2009). Oral histories’ research purpose bridges their status as documents and artifacts: semantic markers such as bound transcripts and digitized audio recordings constitute artifactual evidence of intelligible if distant human agency influencing the transmission and interpretation of document content (Hodder, 2000; Mak, 2014; O’Toole, 1990; Wildemuth, 2009). Limitations of qualitative content analyses pertain to the bounded context and indeterminate authorship of texts.

FINDINGS

Data collection

Data collection of oral histories in September 2022 used website filters to compile an NVivo project and Excel spreadsheets of census and purposive sample data. Internal and external sponsors were sorted and enumerated with website filters and manually entered into Excel spreadsheets. First-phase coding of the census sample refined second-phase coding of the purposive sample filter “Women in Science.” Numerical data for counts refer to completed works and were accurate on October 4, 2022 (Tables 1, 2, and 3). Licenses determine levels of user access to works.

Data analysis of sponsorship

Census sample sponsorship overview

Census sample	Count	Percent census sample
Total oral histories	735	100 %
Internally sponsored	171	23.27 %
35 external sponsors	564	76.73 %

Table 1. Census sample sponsorship percentages

An overview of the census sample shows a total of 735 oral histories and a breakdown of sponsors (Table 1). Of the 735 oral histories in the census sample, internal sponsorship accounts for 171 or 23.27% of the collection. By contrast, external sponsorship accounts for 564 or 76.73%. The census sample overview aids contextualization of the first unit of analysis, external sponsoring entities (Table 2).

Census sample external sponsorship percentages

	Count	Percent census sample
22 external sponsors (for 564 of 735 or 76.73%)		
Pew Charitable Trusts	337	45.85 %
Total of 5 sponsors that funded 19 to 51 oral histories	143	19.46%
Total of 16 sponsors that funded 1 to 18 oral histories	84	11.43%

Table 2. Census sample external sponsorship percentages

A breakdown of 35 external sponsoring entities in the census sample reveals that Pew Charitable Trusts funded almost half of oral histories held in SHI's collection, at 337 of 735 (45.85%) (Table 2). The top five sponsoring entities that follow funded 51 to 19 oral histories for a total of 143 or 19.46%. Rounding out the external sponsors, 16 sponsors that funded 1 to 18 account for 84 or 11.43% of oral histories in the census sample. Even bundled together, the non-Pew sponsors funded fewer oral histories than single sponsor Pew Charitable Trusts (227 or 30.89% versus 45.85%). Pew Charitable Trusts sponsorship predominates funding in the purposive sample, as well.

Purposive sample sponsorship overview

Purposive sample sponsors	Count	Percent purposive	Percent census sample
Total Women in Science (WIS)	93	100.00%	12.65%
Pew Charitable Trusts (WIS)	56	60.22%	7.62%
Internally sponsored and non-Pew external (WIS)	37	39.78%	5.03%

Table 3. Purposive sample sponsorship percentages

Of 93 transcripts in the purposive sample filtered for Women in Science (WIS), 56 (60.22%) are Pew-sponsored while 37 (39.78%) are internally sponsored or non-Pew. Coding samples temporally, transcripts in the census sample date from 1979 to 2021 while the purposive sample's range is 1986 to 2017, and Pew-sponsored transcripts date from 1989 to 2008. In sum, quantitative and temporal dimensions focus the Pew-sponsored oral history project relative to sponsorship in the census and purposive samples. The second unit of analysis is transcript documentation.

Data analysis of an oral history transcript

The following documentation for the official transcript of Brenda L. Bass exemplifies the agency of multiple stakeholders in the oral history project of which it is part. Front matter includes the Pew Charitable Trust oral history project description and statements by the original project entity, and the rights holder (Tables 4, 5, 6).

This oral history is part of a series supported by a grant from the Pew Charitable Trusts based on the Pew Scholars Program in the Biomedical Sciences. This collection is an important resource for the history of biomedicine, recording the life and careers of young, distinguished biomedical scientists and of Pew Biomedical Scholar Advisory Committee members.

Table 4. Pew Charitable Trust oral history project description

This oral history was completed under the auspices of the Oral History Project, University of California, Los Angeles (Copyright © 1996, The Regents of the University of California) and is made possible through the generosity of Pew Charitable Trusts.

Table 5. Statement by the original project entity

The Chemical Heritage Foundation (CHF) serves the community of the chemical and molecular sciences, and the wider public, by treasuring the past, educating the present, and inspiring the future. CHF maintains a world-class collection of materials that document the history and heritage of the chemical and molecular sciences, technologies, and industries; encourages research in CHF collections; and carries out a program of outreach and interpretation in order to advance an understanding of the role of the chemical and molecular sciences, technologies, and industries in shaping society.

Table 6. Statement by the rights holder

Entities are the presumed authors of these texts. Concomitantly, authorship of structured sections of the interview, such as the abstract, table of contents, and index, is attributed to individual project stakeholders who provided

metadata and editing work (not shown). Mapping oral history documentation to bibliographic fields, the citation for the work in the Othmer Library catalogs co-authorship of the work in the title (Table 7) and entity statements in bibliographic fields for notes (not shown).

Brenda L. Bass interview conducted by Andrea R. Maestresjuan at University of Utah, Salt Lake City, UT. (Philadelphia: Chemical Heritage Foundation, Oral History Transcript 0412).
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Table 7. Citation, per Othmer Library catalog entry

RESULTS

Sponsorship of oral history projects and documentary practices for transcripts

The context established for content analysis techniques in the work in progress centers on two units of analysis: one, sponsors of oral history projects in the census sample and in a purposive sample filtered for Women in Science, and two, documentary practices for a transcript in the purposive sample representative of Pew sponsorship. First, data analysis demonstrates the range of 564 external sponsors and predominance of Pew Charitable Trusts among them (337 or 45.85%). Second, documentary practices for a Pew-sponsored transcript in the purposive sample include statements by multiple entities in the transcript's front matter. Results demonstrate that oral history project documentation avoids specificity as to how the project coalesced, the advisory committee's composition, the number of interviewees and interviewers in the project, how interview pairs were chosen and matched, and other details that would contextualize interviews within the project's historiographic theme. In the work, by contrast, attributions for structured elements of interview metadata are detailed. To triangulate oral history project documentary practices with bibliographic metadata, the Othmer Library's citation of the work catalogs co-authorship by narrator and interviewer in the work's title, and slots entities' statements into notes. Using sensitizing concepts, information use in the Pew oral history project reflects multiple frames of reference, collaborations, and visible and invisible work.

DISCUSSION

Work in progress on information use in oral history projects

The oral history genre offers a window onto the formation of an information resource type that is inherently, even radically, human centered. In its emphasis on the interviewee's whole life perspective in light of a historiographic theme, co-authorship of the work highlights the social construction of knowledge in this genre, as does the context of sponsorship comprising multiple frames of reference for project conception, production, and documentation. In the work in progress two layers of information work tasks emerged. In one, entities performed invisible work in conceptualizing the Pew project and determining interview co-authors. In another, co-authors and metadata creators performed visible work for structured sections of the example transcript. In both layers, stakeholders acted as information professionals—in effect if not in name—by conceptualizing, collaborating, producing, and documenting projects. To fulfill the research question, sensitizing concepts in IP, IW, and COP literatures elucidate the use of information in oral histories as reliant on multiple human agents and entities performing visible and invisible work.

CONCLUSION

This is the first study to focus sensitizing concepts in LIS-HIB research on IP, IW, and COPs as tools to theorize documentary practices as a form of information use in the oral history genre. Qualitative content analysis techniques applied to a purposive sample of oral histories at Science History Institute portray human-centered dimensions of an oral history project as multiple frames of reference that layer invisible and visible work: that of sponsors and institutions, interviewers' and narrators' conjoined historiographic perspectives, and metadata creators' structures for discovery, access, and preservation of the works. In sum, an epistemological framework for oral history projects encompasses the conception, production, and documentation of a project by multiple agents performing layers of visible and invisible information work in collaboration. Three directions for future research include exploring one, oral histories in relation to the data curation lifecycle; two, the role of researchers' social construction of knowledge through use of multiple works in an oral history project, potentially collaborating with co-authors; and three, network analysis of oral history projects. Recommendations include extrapolating collaborative information practices in oral histories to the stewardship of primary sources and attributions of information work.

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